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Broadband Sub-THz Dielectric Waveguides Characterization

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Abstract — In this paper, several plastic fiber for high-speed mmW communications are measured in the sub-THz range using waveguide transitions specifically designed for its characterization. These waveguide transitions have the advantage of being low cost and very broadband. First, rectangular to circular waveguide transitions are introduced. Then circular to plastic waveguide transitions are presented. These transitions are designed and measured at D-band (110-170 GHz) and H-band (220- 330 GHz). Next, the characterization of plastic waveguides of different shapes and in both frequency bands is carried out. Within the two considered bands, the proposed transitions achieve both simulated and measured insertion losses (IL) as low as 1 ± 0.2 dB and 2 dB, respectively. For the plastic fibers, a good agreement between theoretical model and experimental results are obtained with loss per meter varying between 4 and 20 dB/m depending on the fiber geometry and operating frequency.

Keywords — Broadband transition, circular waveguide, D-band, H-band, millimeter-wave, plastic waveguide, polymer microwave fiber (PMF), rectangular waveguide, Sub-THz.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the development of plastic waveguides (WG) has raised considerable attention from both the academic and industrial communities [1]-[4], driven by the enhancements in millimeter-wave integrated circuits (MMICs) performance based on advanced silicon technologies. Recent works have reported RF data transmission through plastic WG, achieving data rates over 50 Gbits/s across distances of several meters [5]-[8].

To the best of the authors' knowledge, only a few works have reported plastic fiber characterization using a Vector Network Analyzer (VNA). For example, [9] presents some measurements at a single frequency (72.70 GHz) using a power meter for several materials and dimension but a study covering sub-THz frequencies has not yet been done. The accurate determination of the attenuation performances of the plastic fibers at these frequencies are paramount in order to have an accurate link budget estimation, and consequently the lowest possible energy consumption. In addition, there is no commercially available suitable WG transition for plastic fibers at D and H bands. Using a WG transition at these frequencies is an alternative approach to antenna coupling [10], [11]. The WG transitions also offer the advantage of

facilitating the insertion and mechanical holding of the plastic fiber for more accurate characterization.

In this paper, section II presents the dimensions of the plastic fibers and the various transitions in the D and H bands. Section III presents the measurement results of the transitions and plastic waveguides. Three different plastic fibers are considered. The first two are: a circular section HDPE fiber of 1.75 mm of diameter and a hollowed cylinder section PTFE fiber of external and internal diameters of 2 mm and 1 mm, respectively. These two fibers have been selected to operate at D-band (100-170 GHz). The third fiber is a circular section PTFE fiber of 0.889 mm of diameter, selected for H-band (220-330 GHz). Simulations presented in this paper were achieved using the CST microwave studio electromagnetic software.

II. TRANSITIONS AND WAVEGUIDE SIZING

A. Circular Waveguide to Dielectric Waveguide Transition

The transition shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 have been designed in order to measure the transmission properties of plastic fiber using a VNA with D-band or H-band extenders having rectangular WG ports (WR-6.5 or WR-3.4, respectively, for each band). The first transition is a connector between the plastic waveguide and the metallic waveguide. This transition adapts the impedance between the sections made of different materials (plastic + air, plastic, air) with different dielectric properties. Thus, varying the diameters of

Fig. 1 Circular waveguide to hollow core waveguide transition used in simulations and experiments: (a) Front view and (b) Cross-section view showing the 5 sections of the transition.

the transition along its axe allows the impedance of the wave to be optimal [12] and provides a mechanical hold. Consequently, section 1 in Fig. 1 is used to couple the electromagnetic field in the plastic waveguide and the emitted electromagnetic field respectively received by the VNA. Sections 2 and 4 provide impedance matching based on step-impedance sections. Finally, the dimensions of sections 3 and 5 are constrained by the diameter of the plastic waveguide (section 3) and the diameter of the WR-standard. The dimensions of the transitions from plastic waveguide to waveguide are shown in Table 1 for the three considered fibers.

Table 1. Dimensions in mm of the transitions for (a) Hollow waveguide in D-band (b) Circular waveguide in D-band (c) Circular waveguide in H-band, with d_i being the diameter and l_i the length of the section i .

Section:	1	2	3	4	5
d_i (a)	1.86	1.9	2	2.2	2.4
l_i (a)	1.7	1.5	1.6	1	1.1
d_i (b)	1.86	1.7	1.76	2.2	2.4
l_i (b)	1.43	1.75	1.6	0.7	1.5
d_i (c)	0.89	0.84	0.9	1.1	1.3
l_i (c)	1	1	1	0.5	1.1

B. Circular to Rectangular Waveguide Transition

The circular to rectangular transition is used to connect the previous transition to the VNA rectangular WG ports. Consequently, the dimensions and shapes of the two ends are imposed. The middle section is rectangular. The dimensions of this rectangular section are as close as possible to a square in order to have a shape that is manufacturable and approaching the rectangle and circular extremities. The transition is 2.4 cm long to allow fixing the transitions to the VNA ports. The dimensions of the two circular to rectangular transitions required for each of the bands are given in Table 2.

Fig. 2. Rectangular to circular transition used in simulations and experiments: (a) Front view and (b) Cross-section view showing the 3 sections of the transition.

Table 2. Dimensions in mm of the circular to rectangular transitions at (a) D-band and (b) H-band, with d_i being the diameter, h_i the height, w_i the width and l_i the length of section i .

Section	1	2	3
d_i (a)	-	-	1.65
h_i / w_i (a)	0.8 / 1.6	0.9 / 1.5	-
l_i (a)	20	2	2
d_i (b)	-	-	0.99
h_i / w_i (b)	0.43 / 0.86	0.6 / 0.8	-
l_i (b)	20	2	2

C. Plastic Fibers Propagation Analysis

For the plastic fibers, also known as dielectric WG, in order to have as little dispersion as possible, it is preferable to remain in the single-mode frequency band. For circular dielectric WG this results in the HE_{11} mode, and this mode is the only one propagated if the following condition is fulfilled [12]:

$$0 < f < f_c = \frac{2.405}{2\pi a} \frac{c_0}{\sqrt{\epsilon_{r1} - \epsilon_{r2}}}, \quad (1)$$

where a is the radius of the waveguide, c_0 the wave velocity in vacuum, ϵ_{r1} the permittivity of the waveguide and ϵ_{r2} the permittivity of the medium surrounding the waveguide. In our study, this medium is air. In order to predict dielectric losses, Elsasser's theory is applied [13]:

$$\alpha = 4.343 \frac{2\pi\epsilon_r \tan \delta}{\lambda_0} R, \quad (2)$$

with $\tan \delta$ the loss tangents, λ_0 the wavelength in vacuum, and R a parameter from the integration of the electromagnetic field for the HE_{11} mode. Due to the size of the radius plastic waveguide, the parameter R is assumed to be equal to the following equation, unless otherwise specified:

$$R = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon_r}} \quad (3)$$

III. MEASUREMENT RESULTS

A. Measurement Set-up

The WG transitions have been fabricated using Computer Numerical control (CNC) and Electrical Discharge Machining (EDM) procedures. The plastic fibers have been sourced from existing plastic fiber manufacturers and were originally intended for other applications (inject printing, medical applications). The diameters were selected between the available dimensions to fit the target communication bands: the D-band (110-170GHz) and H-band (220-330 GHz). The measurements have been made using the Rhodes & Schwarz ZVA24 with D-band and H-band extenders. Calibrations were carried out using the Thru-Open-Short-Match (TOSM) and Thru-Reflect-Line (TRL) methods at the VNA extender ports. The fibers are plugged into the transitions and hold in place using a foam cylinder made of expanded polyethylene with a 29 Kg/m³ density and a Plexiglas holding ring fixed to the transition external section, as shown in Fig. 3. Some other foam handlers are added along the fiber body to limit the contact with surfaces (these foams handlers play the role of a coating).

Fig. 3. Measuring setup.

B. Transitions Measurement Results

The transitions are measured in back to back as shown in Fig. 4. Due to the symmetry of the structure, the S_{21} of a single transition is considered half the measured S_{21} . The result for the D-band transition for the 1.75 mm HDPE plastic fiber is shown in Fig. 5, compared to the simulations. The ringing is due to reflections that occur due to air cavities resulting from impedance steps. The simulated transition average insertion loss (half of the one shown in the figure) varies between 1 and 0.5 dB across the band, and the experimental insertion loss results are less than 1 dB higher in average. Very similar results are obtained for D-band transition for the 2 mm PTFE plastic fiber.

Fig. 6 shows the same experiment for the H-band transitions. The simulated insertion losses are of the same order than in the D-band case as well as the difference with the measurements. This can be explained by the manufacturing tolerances, which were 60 μm , and by the electrical contact, which is assumed perfect in simulations, whereas this is not necessarily the case in reality.

C. Plastic Fibers Measurements Results

The measurement set-up used to characterize the plastic fibers was shown in Fig. 3. The plastic waveguide is bent as little as possible to avoid adding losses due to bending or twisting [14]. To improve the accuracy, several lengths are measured (1 m, 2 m and 4 m for the D-band fibers, and 50 cm, 1.5 m and 2 m of the H-band fibers). In order to obtain the dielectric losses, the average losses α per unit length are obtained from the transmission coefficient obtained for several lengths by using the following expression:

$$\alpha = \frac{S_{21}(L_2) - S_{21}(L_1)}{L_2 - L_1}, \quad (4)$$

where L_1 and L_2 are two different fiber lengths. Fig. 7 left shows the transmission coefficient measured for three lengths of 1.75 mm circular section HDPE fiber and also the results of applying (4) to each pair length differences. The various α curves obtained are averaged and shown in the right panel compared to the theoretical model of (2) with $\epsilon_r = 2.4$ and $\tan \delta = 4 \cdot 10^{-4}$. The experimental value is in good agreement with the theory. The variations visible in the measurements are due to the wave reflected in the plastic waveguide. The loss per unit length for this fiber varies from 6 to 10 dB/m in the 110 to 170 GHz frequency range.

The same procedure is applied to the other two fibers and the results are shown in Fig. 8, on the left for the 2 mm hollowed cylinder cross-section PTFE fiber at D-band, and on the right for the 0.889 mm circular cross-section PTFE fiber at H-band. The loss of the 2 mm PTFE fiber vary between 4 and 6 dB/m in the 110 to 170 GHz frequency range. The measurements closely follow the theoretical model with $\epsilon_r = 2.1$ and $\tan \delta = 2.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$. Unlike circular waveguides, hollow circular waveguides exhibit less ripple. However, when the frequency is higher than 150 GHz, peaks can be observed in measurements, and are attributed the end of the single-mode band. In addition, because of its shape, the hollow

Fig. 4. Measurement set-up for the characterization of the transitions.

Fig. 5. $|S_{21}|$ for a 1.75 mm circular to rectangular WR-6.5 waveguide transition at D-band frequencies.

Fig. 6. $|S_{21}|$ for a 0.889 mm circular to WR-3.4 rectangular waveguide transition in back to back at H-band frequencies.

Fig. 7. Left: $|S_{21}|$ for various lengths of 1.75 mm HDPE fibre and extracted loss per unit length using (4). Right: comparison between the experimental α per unit length and model of (2).

guide is more likely to be deformed and therefore to show a higher mode. The H-band 0.889 mm circular cross-section PTFE fiber shows a loss varying between 9 and 20 dB/m in the 220 to 300 GHz frequency range. It also shows a good fitting to the model with $\epsilon_r = 2.08$ and $\tan \delta = 4.4 \cdot 10^{-4}$. However, this time the R parameter of (2) needs to be scaled with frequency as explained in [9] and [13] in order to correctly fit the measurements. The measured loss per meter shows significant ringing. The calibration is necessarily more

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REFERENCES

- [1] S. Fukuda *et al.*, "A 12.5+12.5 Gb/s full-duplex plastic waveguide interconnect," in *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 46, no. 12, pp. 3113-3125, Dec. 2011.
- [2] F. Voineau *et al.*, "A 12 Gb/s 64QAM and OFDM compatible millimeter-wave communication link using a novel plastic waveguide design," *IEEE Radio and Wireless Symposium (RWS)*, Anaheim, CA, USA, 2018.
- [3] L. Van Thienen, Y. Zhang, and P. Reynaert, "Bidirectional communication circuits for a 120-GHz PMF data link in 40-nm CMOS," in *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 53, no. 7, pp. 2023-2031, July 2018.
- [4] A. Standaert and P. Reynaert, "Analysis of hollow circular polymer waveguides at millimeter wavelengths," in *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques*, vol. 64, no. 10, pp. 3068-3077.
- [5] J.L. González-Jiménez *et al.*, "Channel bonding transceivers for efficient 100 Gb/s and beyond wireless and plastic waveguide communications," *29th IEEE International Conference on Electronics, Circuits and Systems (ICECS)*, Glasgow, United Kingdom, 2022.
- [6] J. Vaes *et al.*, "Plastic microwave fibers at millimeter-wave and THz frequencies as a low cost data link," *IEEE MTT-S International Microwave Symposium (IMS)*, Atlanta, GA, USA, 2021.
- [7] H. -I. Song *et al.*, "A 50Gb/s PAM-4 bi-directional dielectric waveguide link with carrier synchronization using PI-based costas loop," *IEEE International Solid-State Circuits Conference (ISSCC)*, San Francisco, CA, USA, 2022.
- [8] K. Dens *et al.*, "A 100-Gb/s 3-m dual-band PAM-4 plastic waveguide link with 1.9 pJ/bit/m efficiency in 28-nm CMOS," *IEEE Radio Frequency Integrated Circuits Symposium (RFIC)*, San Diego, CA, USA, 2023, pp. 13-16.
- [9] D. Jablonski, "Attenuation characteristics of circular dielectric waveguide at millimeter wavelengths," *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques*, vol. 26, no. 9, pp. 667-671, Sep. 1978.
- [10] T. Lampersberger *et al.*, "A novel chip to PCB-half-embedded waveguide transition," *51st European Microwave Conference (EuMC)*, London, United Kingdom, 2022, pp. 389-392.
- [11] J.L. González-Jiménez *et al.*, "A 56.32 Gb/s 16-QAM link over dielectric fiber using a D-band channel bonding transceiver," *51st European Microwave Conference (EuMC)*, London, United Kingdom, 2022, pp. 197-200.
- [12] D. M. Pozar, *Microwave Engineering*. 3rd edition. Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Son, Inc, 2005.
- [13] W. M. Elsasser, "Attenuation in a dielectric circular rod," *J.App. Physics* 20, p 1193, Dec. 1949.
- [14] S. Lagoug *et al.*, "Twisting effects on x-shaped millimeter-wave plastic waveguides," *IEEE MTT-S International Microwave Symposium (IMS)*, Washington, MD, USA, 2024.
- [15] Li, Y., *et al.* "Transmission characteristics of flexible low-loss solid circular polymer dielectric waveguides for sub-thz applications," *J Infrared Milli Terahz Waves* vol.44, pp. 110-133. 2023.
- [16] F. Distler, J. Schür, and M. Vossiek, "In-depth characterization of a dielectric waveguide for mmW transmission line applications," *IEEE 22nd Workshop on Signal and Power Integrity (SPI)*, Brest, France, 2018, pp. 1-4.
- [17] F. Distler, M. Sippel, J. Schür, G. Gold, K. Helmreich, and M. Vossiek, "Additively manufactured dielectric waveguides for advanced concepts for millimeter-wave interconnects," *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques*, vol. 67, no. 11, pp. 4298-4307, Nov. 2019.

Fig. 8. Dielectric losses for the 2 mm hollow core plastic fiber at D-band, left, and for the 0.889 mm circular section plastic fiber at H-band, right.

challenging in H-band than in D-band because of the increased bandwidth. Furthermore, the waveguide seems to become multimode around 300 GHz. Finally, at these frequencies, manufacturing tolerances, surface roughness and the placement of the plastic waveguide in the transition have a bigger impact on the attenuation characteristics. The results obtained for the three fibers are summarized in Table 3, including the material parameters used in the theoretical model of (2).

Table 3. Summary of parameters for the three characterized plastic fibres.

Fiber	1.75 mm HDPE	2 mm PTFE	0.889 mm PTFE
Freq. (GHz)	110-170	110-170	220-330
α (dB/m)	6-10	4-6	9-20
ϵ_r	2.4	2.1	2.08
$\tan \delta$	$4 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$4.4 \cdot 10^{-4}$
R in (2)	$1/\sqrt{\epsilon_r}$	$1/\sqrt{\epsilon_r}$	0.54-0.72

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

There are only a few works reporting loss measurements for plastic fibers (or dielectric waveguides) at mmW approaching the sub-THz frequency range as summarized in Table 4. Extending such prior works to the sub-THz range, this paper presents the experimental characterization of two fiber candidates for communications at the D-band from 110 to 170 GHz and one for the H-band from 220 to 330 GHz. The lowest loss is obtained for the PTFE hollowed fiber at D-band, with values ranging from 4 to 6 dB/m. The HDPE rod displays slightly higher losses. The H-band PTFE rod has a largely varying loss from 9 to 20 dB/m across the measured frequency range. These values are coherent with previous results shown in Table 4 when extrapolated to higher frequencies. The paper presents also five different transitions designed and fabricated to enable reliable measurements using VNAs. Simulation and measurement results show that the insertion losses of the transitions are between 1 and 3 dB. These results are critical for determining the fiber selection for future dielectric waveguide high-speed communication systems as those investigated in the COREnext European project.

Table 4. Results from previous works.

Ref	[9]	[15]	[16]
Fiber	2.01 mm PTFE	1.5 mm PTFE	2.54x1.27 mm HDPE
Freq. (GHz)	71	90-140	75-110
α (dB/m)	0.83	1-4	1.9-2.2
ϵ_r	2.08	-	2.25
$\tan \delta$	$1.9 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-	$5 \cdot 10^{-4}$